

Project Monitoring Report

Western Sahara War Archives - A Monitoring Database for the II War in Western Sahara

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Abstract

The *Western Sahara War Archives* (WSWA) project is a website, developed by the *Center for African Studies of the University of Porto* (CEAUP), design to accompany the II Western Sahara War.

This report aims to assess the performance of the project at the end of its first 12 (twelve) months of activity, through the statistical analysis of a set of parameters. Therefore, the information collected, will be presented and discussed over 9 points: its context (1), its creation (2), the operations protocol (3), the work teams (4), the difficulties encountered (5), project objectives (6), evaluation metrics and their results (7), future actions (8) and its conclusions.

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Introduction

With the resumption of the War in *Western Sahara*, a series of doubts gained a new dimension. Faced with the inaction of the *International Institutions*, the unfavorable or absent tone of the *Media* in relation to questions about *Western Sahara*, what would be the tone of the approach to the resumption of war? Would they be exempt and would they only demonstrate the facts? Would they broach the subject of the resumption of war? Or would there be no mention of the events? What will be the impact on the Saharawi populations? Bearing in mind that the vast majority live in refugee camps in Algeria, what will be the impact of this new conflict on them? And by extension, what is the impact on populations living in the so-called “Occupied Territories”?

Considering that, since 1963, *Western Sahara* has been a *Non-Autonomous Territory*, under the *article 73 of Chapter XI of the United Nations Charter*, in practicality, it has been in a state of siege since 1960. The first clashes were against colonial power, *Spain*, and later, against *Mauritania* and *Morocco*. The territorial mass that constitutes *Western Sahara* has been under effective military occupation, by the latter, since 1975.

During the 80's of the 20th Century, the territory would end up being divided into two parts, by a military wall, with Morocco having occupied about 80% of the total territory - the most useful part and rich in natural resources - *SADR*, the remaining 20%. This artificial barrier, became known as the "*Berm*", whose physical expansion continues to the present day, having already been considered as the largest military wall of the contemporary era.

In 1991, after several attempts at agreement and negotiations, it was possible to establish a ceasefire agreement between the *POLISARIO Front* and *Morocco*. Agreement that would be violated in the middle of the fourth quarter of 2020 by *Morocco*, thus restarting the armed conflict with *POLISARIO's* declaration of the end of the ceasefire.

In order to carry out the monitoring of war events on the ground, and to understand how events would be reported in the rest of the world, the CEAUP Research Group number 2: African policies and territories, a work team dedicated to the theme: Internal and External Policy of African States, developed a project to collect and process data related to the war.

The intention of this report is to present a first assessment of the activities, developed work, and its impact on the academic world and on the discourse surrounding the conflict, which the project had in its first year of existence. With that in mind, this report will be divided as follows:

1. Project Context;
2. Project Creation:
 - a. Conceptualization of the Idea;
 - b. Implementation of the Idea;

3. Operation Protocol:
 - a. Documents:
 - i. Typology;
 - ii. Sources;
 - iii. Collection Method;
 - iv. Intended Subjects;
 - b. News:
 - i. Typology;
 - ii. Sources;
 - iii. Collection Method;
 - iv. Intended Subjects;
 - c. Military Resources:
 - i. Typology;
 - ii. Sources;
 - iii. Collection Method;
 - iv. Intended Subjects;
4. Work methodology:
 - a. Research Teams:
 - i. Typology;
 - ii. Composition;
5. Difficulties;
6. Project Objectives;
7. Evaluation;
8. Future Actions;

The accumulated experiences of other projects, lead us to conclude that the growing influence of the mass media, such as *Twitter*, *Facebook* and *YouTube*, the so-called *Social Media*, along with a, albeit decreasing, influence of the traditional Media, oblige us to carry out a serious analysis of all the functional resources involved in the project, in order to obtain a clear image of our presence in these spaces of debate.

We must also bear in mind that the, constant aggregation and dissemination of information and sources, in an impartial and unbiased way, is one of the most important aspects, which contrasts with orthodox solutions, obfuscation of sources and partiality. This requires high precision, evaluation and definition of goals, sources, evaluation criteria and exclusion of primary and secondary sources, in their most varied forms.

Therefore, the effort to analyze and monitor the project evaluation process is a priority, in order to understand its impact. Hence, it is important to be sure that the methodologies used in the project were the most correct.

Consequently, a set of metrics and statistical data will be presented on the performance of the website developed by the CEAUP Team. The evaluation process will consist of the following elements:

1. Statistical analysis of the contents produced:

- A) News (typology, formats, language and country of broadcast);
- B) Military Data;

C) Social Media.

2. An analysis of a varied set of statistical data and performance metrics from the website itself, trying to answer:

- a) In what way, the website, impacted the establishment of knowledge of this conflict?
- b) How this knowledge spread through the scientific community, and society in general?

3. After understanding the overview of the project, possible guidelines will be drawn for the future management of the project, in order to fill the gaps found.

1. Project Context

On 13 November 2020, after one of a series of peaceful protests carried out by part of the Saharawi population in territories outside the control of *Morocco*, the *Moroccan Forces Armées Royales (FAR)* attacked Saharawi civilians, by entering a buffer zone to carry out the attack. The *Saharawi Arab Democratic Republic (SADR)*, faced with the inaction of the International Institutions, represented on the ground by the *United Nations Mission for the Referendum in Western Sahara (MINURSO)*, denounced the violation of the ceasefire agreement by part of the other signatory, *Morocco*, assuming this act, as an intentional act of war by *Morocco* against the Saharawi population, and through transitive property¹, against *SADR*.

Since 1991, the year in which a ceasefire agreement was signed between *Morocco* and the *Frente Popular de Liberación de Saguía el Hamra y Río de Oro (POLISARIO Front)*, the region has lived in a situation of high social tension and in a climate of possible resumption of hostilities at any time. The successive failures of international policy, which failed to proceed with the referendum proposal and a long list of human rights violations by *Morocco*, as well as the Saharawi natural resources, being violently and illegally used by *Morocco*, led to the total disbelief in a solution in accordance with *UN* resolutions and international law for the peaceful self-determination of the Saharawi people.

Morocco opened three unauthorized entrances to the “*Berm*”, in the Buffer Zone of *Guergarat*, that is, inside the space that *MINURSO* was supposed to monitor.

This failure of supervision on the part of *MINURSO*, which thus becomes yet another actor of instability, led to a situation in which the option of resuming the war was the only and inevitable conclusion. Therefore, *SADR*, denounced the violation of article 3 of the Ceasefire Agreement by *Morocco*, paving the way again for the hostility that followed.

The first European journalists, were invited in October 2021 by *SADR*, to travel to the scene of the conflict.

¹ The populations of a Nation represent that Nation, so it can be inferred that any and every attack against these populations is an attack against the Nation itself.

2. Project Creation

The risk of this conflict becoming invisible in the eyes of the world is real. The political pressure, resulting from economic interests, that exists in the West, not to resolve the situation, combined with the emergence of the *SARS-CoV-2* pandemic, lead the *CEAUP*, which monitors and follows events on the African continent, promptly proposed to develop a project to monitor the situation on the ground.

It is never too much to remember the weight and meaning of these problems, since they condition, from the first moment, the format/type of project that could be considered; the method of collecting and processing quantitative and qualitative data; the collection, analysis and criticism of sources.

The current structure of the organization was one of the first constraints that the team took into account, since it would be necessary to implement a work methodology and form a team to carry out the follow-up. The second was the aforementioned *SARS-CoV-2* pandemic, which made it impossible to travel to the field and, consequently, to collect data on the ground. Another problem, was the lack of primary and secondary sources, partly due to *Morocco's* position, partly due to the impossibility of travel by journalists and researchers to the field. The lack of written information and lack of collection, analysis and criticism of existing sources, was another. The political instability in the region and the difficulty in obtaining travel authorizations to an active war scenario, have also played a role.

However, both the scope and meaning of these problems, have allowed *CEAUP* to obtain the perception of the difficulties, but have also helped in the identification, preparation and composition of the resources that would be necessary to solve them.

a) Conceptualization of the Idea

Due to the existing limitations and constraints, it would be absolutely impossible to send a researcher, or a group of researchers, to the field, so that the data collection could be carried out *in loco*. This impossibility also affected the travel of journalists and photojournalists. At least, not until the *SARS-CoV-2* Pandemic transformed from Pandemic state into Endemic state. Since the first forms of the medical action protocol dictated: a) the need for a prolonged confinement, in order to contain the spread of the virus; b) isolation of infected people; c) prohibition of any type of travel (local, trans-municipal, inter-district, inter-regional and international) by any means or route.

As it was not possible to collect data in this way, the *CEAUP* team, based on past experiences, both individual and collective, decided to:

1. That it would be necessary to create a multidisciplinary team;
2. That the team would have to work on a voluntary basis until funding was obtained;
3. The creation of a website that aggregates the data collected;
4. That this team would be composed with elements trained in:

- a) **History** - in order to work with multiple types of sources, often contradictory, would be need one element with a background in History, to be responsible for the work methodology, collection, analysis and criticism of these sources;
- b) **Archeology** - in order to guarantee at least on element with practical knowledge of collecting archaeological, historical and geographical information, in order to plan future interventions on the ground, distinguish possible patterns in the terrain and in the material culture that could be found (munitions, cartridges, combat vehicles, logistics vehicles, possible anthropomorphized locations, ...)
- c) **Geography** - in order to guarantee one element with the technical knowledge of map making and cartography, so that it was possible to use *GIS* technology;
- d) **International Relations**– would be need one element familiar with international policy and human rights issues, in order to properly evaluated, in the lights of International Law and Human Rights, what was happening on the ground;
- e) **ICT**– remote monitoring of the events would be the best solution, for the moment, for the data collection and storage. Thus, making it necessary, the presence of at least one element, who was familiar with ICT technology ad web base systems;

b) Implementation of the Idea

With the Idea conceptualized, the next phase was to implement it. For this a website was need to the aggregator of a set of information

In order to broaden the reach of the site, the chosen domain was **.com** as it is a general domain, one of the best known and most used by companies that have a presence in the digital space. The base for the site was WordPress base.

The name chosen was *Western Sahara War Archives*, as it was thought and designed to be an archive for the events. The same philosophy is reflected in its Logo (Figure 1). Therefore, the full address for the site is: <https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/>

Figure 1- WSWA Logo

PROJECT MONITORING REPORT: WESTERN SAHARA WAR ARCHIVES – A MONITORING DATABASE FOR THE II WAR IN WESTERN SAHARA

Figure 2- General Appearance of the Site

It was also decided that the work team would focus on 3 (three) major themes:

1. *Official Documents*, designated as *Documents* (Figure 4- Documents Menu)
2. *News*, designated as *Media* (Figure 3- News Menu)
3. *War documents*, designated as *War Data* (Figure 5- War Data Menu)

PROJECT MONITORING REPORT: WESTERN SAHARA WAR ARCHIVES – A MONITORING DATABASE FOR THE II WAR IN WESTERN SAHARA

Figure 4- Documents Menu

Figure 3- News Menu

Figure 5- War Data Menu

3. Operation Protocol

As an independent, reputable and impartial *R&D* Center, it was established, by the CEAUP team, that all and any information that addressed the theme of war, would be collected by the 3 (three) teams.

Thus, fields were created for both sides of the conflict, and any and all official information and/or issued by official entities, or by independent media, would be treated with the same impartiality.

Figure 6- Overall Collection Process Schematics

The following figures represents the logic of the work developed by the aforementioned teams

a) Documents

Figure 7- Documents Collection Process Schematics

b) News

Figure 8-News Collection Process Schematics

c) Military Resources

Figure 9-Military Information Collection Process Schematics

d) Social Media

Figure 10-Social Media Collection Process Schematics

For more information, consult the team's *Editorial Note*, which can be seen and consulted in the *About Us* section on the website:

<https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/about-wswa/>

4. Research Teams

In methodological terms, the work team was divided into 3 (three) sub teams, to be named:

- a) *News Team*
- b) *Statistics Team*
- c) *Twitter Team*

This subdivision intended to create small cores, dedicated to work with a set of specific data, nevertheless interconnected, in order to facilitate data processing.

Despite having different subjects matters, the first two teams employ the same methodology, the difference lies in the sources used.

4.1. Work Methodology

a) *News Team*

The news team's main function is to analyze news and official documents that address the following topics:

- ✓ Mention of the War in *Western Sahara*;
- ✓ Violation of *Human Rights* in the Occupied Territories;
- ✓ Documentation issued by official entities in which there is direct reference to *Western Sahara*, the Occupied Territories and the War in *Western Sahara*;

The news is obtained through a system of Google Alerts, built around the following **Keywords**:

- "Ws Wa"
- Guergarat
- Polisario
- saara ocidental
- Sahara Occidental
- Sahara occidentale
- Sahara Ocidental
- Västra Sahara
- Vestre Sahara
- Vestsahara
- Westelijke Sahara
- western sahara
- western sahara war archives
- westsahara
- Западная Сахара
- סהרה המערבית
- الصحراء الغربية

- 撒哈拉沙漠西部
- 西サハラ

Triage Criteria:

- 1) Being news published by reputable newspapers or journalistic entities (e.g., *Washington Post*; *El País*; *Lusa*; *Der Spiegel*; ...);
- 2) Not being posts from Blogs, Vlogs, or merely opinion channels;
- 3) Not being reposts of Blogs, Vlogs, or merely opinion channels;
- 4) Being videos or reports from reputable sources;
 - a) Videos or reports from reliable sources are collected and stored on a device prepared for the case, to be repost later in a proper channel;
- 5) Address the defined theme;
- 6) They do not address the defined themes.

Results are received daily, in two specially prepared email inbox. On average, between 100-400 notifications are received, for triage, daily in each email inbox. This volume is subject to a triage, in order to separate the news by:

- News that meets the criteria;
- News that does not meet the criteria.

After triage, the news that meet the evaluation criteria are collected in PDF format.

The last step is the upload to the website. This also has a set of rules and procedures that must be followed. Thus, during the upload procedure, it is necessary to fill in a form with the following categories:

1. Title in the original language;
2. A title in English
 - a. If the news article does not have the title in English, a translation of it will be made;
 - b. This is done in order to augment its visibility and searchability by the search engines like Google;
3. Upload of the PDF of the news article;
4. Link to the original news;
5. Original date of the news;
6. Issuer;
7. Language of Issue;
8. Country of Issue;
9. Typology;
10. *Key words*.

This form is mandatory, and the upload of material is only possible after completing the input of the requested data in all fields.

This team is also in charge of collecting *Official Documentations*. And in this sense, whenever there is a mention of a new document, whether through a press release, or a

news article, or through a periodic active search on the Institutions' websites, this official document is collected.

Evaluation Criteria for the Documentation:

1. Documents published by Official Institutions:
 - a) *ONU*;
 - b) *AU*;
 - c) *EU*;
 - d) *NATO*;
 - e) National Parliaments;
 - f) National Courts;
 - g) International Courts;
2. Address the defined theme:
 - a) If Yes, they are collected.
 - b) If No, they are not collected.
3. The collection is made in PDF format.

Mandatory fields to fill in the form:

- 1) Title in the original language;
- 2) Title in English, and if the *Official Document* does not have the title in English, a translation will be made;
- 3) Upload of the PDF of the *Official Document*;
- 4) Link to the original *Official Document*;
- 5) Original date of the *Official Document*;
- 6) Issuer;
- 7) Language of Issue;
- 8) Issuing Country:
 - a) For the determination of this point, the capitals of the countries are used, and in the case of institutions, the location of their headquarters is used as a determining factor. Eg: UN-New York-USA; EU-Brussels-Belgium;
- 9) Typology:
 - a) *Western Sahara*:
 - i. *Official Documents* published by *SADR* via *SPS*;
 - b) Morocco:
 - i. *Official Documents* published by News Agencies belonging to the State;
 - ii. *Official Documents* published by the Government;
 - c) *UN*:
 - i. Secretary General;
 - ii. Security Council;
 - iii. High Commissioner for Refugees;
 - d) *AU*:
 - i. Assembly of Heads of State;
 - ii. Executive Council;
 - iii. Permanent Representatives Committee;
 - iv. Pan-African Parliament;
 - v. Peace and Security Council;

- vi. African Commission on Human and People's Rights;
- vii. African Court on Human and People's Rights;
- viii. AU Commission on International Law;
- e) Europe:
 - i. Parliaments of European countries;
 - ii. Heads of State of European countries;
 - iii. Institutions from European countries;
 - iv. EU Parliament;
 - v. EU Justice Court;
 - vi. European Commission;
 - vii. EU MP Groups;
- f) Africa:
 - i. African countries parliaments;
 - ii. Heads of State of African countries;
 - iii. Institutions from African countries;
- g) America:
 - i. Parliaments of American countries;
 - ii. Heads of State of American countries;
 - iii. Institutions from American countries;
- h) Asia:
 - i. Parliaments of Asian countries;
 - ii. Heads of State of Asian countries;
 - iii. Institutions from Asian countries;

10) Key words/Tags

- b) Statistics Team

The statistics and maps team's main function are: the statistical and cartographic treatment of the data collected in the *War Communiqués* and by the statistical data generated by the news team. It does not have an email prepared to receive the military reports, designated as *War Communiqués*, as these are published on the *SPS* website.

Since Morocco continues to claim that there is no war, there is still no military data on its side, however as soon as the situation is reversed, that data will be collected, processed and posted on the website as well.

Military data is treated as follows:

- Collection:
 - 1) Search for *War Communiqués* on the *SPS* website:
 - a) The *War Communiqués* are published in Spanish, French and Arabic;
 - 2) Collection of *War Communiqués* in PDF format, in Spanish:
 - a) The Castilian language was selected for reasons of logical consistency, since it was the language in which, the *War Communiqués*, presented more data related to the war and offered additional information about the attacks;
 - 3) Data is collected daily.
- Treatment of Information:
 - 1) Date identification:
 - a) The analysis period is 7 days;
 - i. Data collection starts on Monday;
 - ii. Data collection is completed on Sunday;

- iii. Additional Requirement: check the following Monday, after the completion of the data collection, in order to confirm if more data were added, about the attacks on Sunday's, which were not present in the *Sunday War Communiqué*;
- 2) Identification of attack sites:
- a) In order to facilitate the reading of this data, and after several meetings with Saharawi entities, it was possible to establish the following divisions:
 - i. Super region:
 1. Designated as Military Region;
 2. There are 3 (three) Military Regions, namely:
 - a) *Oued Daraa*
 - i. Demarcated on maps in Green;
 - ii. Demarcated in the tables in Green;
 - iii. Demarcated in the graphics in Green;
 - b) *Saguia El Hamara*
 - i. Demarcated on maps in Yellow;
 - ii. Demarcated in the tables in Yellow;
 - iii. Demarcated in the graphics in Yellow;
 - c) *Rio de Oro*
 - i. Demarcated on maps in Red;
 - ii. Demarcated in the tables in Red;
 - iii. Demarcated in the graphics in Red;
 3. Each Military Region is designated by the acronym RM+n°:
 - a) R- Região (Region in Portuguese), M-Militar (Militar in Portuguese);
 - b) Therefore, the Military Regions are:
 - i. RM1-Oued Daraa;
 - ii. RM2-Saguia El Hamara;
 - iii. RM3-Rio de Oro;
 - ii. Sectors:
 1. Each Military Region is subdivided into sectors;
 2. Each sector is designated by the acronym S+n° (S1, S2, S3, ...);
 - a) S- Sector (Sector in Portuguese);
 3. There are 13 (thirteen) sectors, namely:
S1-Aaga
S2-Touzigui
S3-EL Mahabes
S4-Farisa
S5-Haouza
S6-Smara
S7-Amgala
S8-Guelta Zemmour
S9-Oum Dreiga
S10-El Bagari
S11-Auserd
S12-Techla
S13-Bir Guendouz
 4. S1-S4 are located within Oued Daraa;
 5. S5-S8 are located within Saguia El Hamara;

6. S9-S13 are located within Rio de Oro;
- 3) *Sectors* Identification;
 - a) The *Sectors* are the only consistent location mentioned by the *War Communiqués*;
- 4) *Zones* Identification:
 - a) A *Zone* consists in a designated location within the *Sector*;
 - b) Identification of the *Zones* within the *Sectors* where, at least, 1 (one) attack were reported;
 - c) Without a clear identification of the *Zone*, the attack will be counted as an attack, according to the reported number, in the stated *Sector*;
 - i. They will also be classified as *Unknown*;
 - d) Through the crossing of data, whenever there is a location that appears registered in two sectors, that location will be considered as a *Border Zone*, being marked and/or remarked on the border between *Sectors* on the maps;
 - e) Collection of the names of the locations in order to create a Database on the Spelling of Names;
 - f) This Database will be turn into a future publication as a Glossary of Names;
- 5) Quantification of the number of attacks:
 - a) Without the specific mention of a number, the attack is counted as 1 (one) attack;
- 6) All these data are placed in an Excel sheet prepared for this purpose;
- 7) Extra information mentioned in *War Communiqués*, such as destruction of specific bases, movement of troops, destruction of radars, ..., are mentioned as follows:
 - a) Inside the Excel cell: Name of the location (n^o*);
 - b) Bottom of the table: under Obs.: (n^o*) additional information;
- 8) After compiling the Data, they are transformed into Graphics:
 - a) There are 3 types of charts:
 - i. Bars for counting attacks, divided by Regions and Week Comparison;
 - ii. Circulars counting percentages;
 - iii. Linear showing the progression of attacks;
- 9) After completing the Excel, the data are also transformed into geographic information, using a *GIS* program:
 - a) Program used for creating maps is *QGIS 3.16 Hannover*;
 - b) The program used to create the interactive map displayed on the website Home Page is *ArcGIS Online*;
 - c) The base of the map is *OpenStreetMap*;
 - d) Signaling of attacks is made with the international symbol of explosion;
 - e) *Unknown* will be placed, in the maps, near the main City of the Sector, in order to count the attack as an unidentified attack in the sector;
 - f) Due to the lack of accurate geographic information, all attacks will be placed close to the military wall;
 - g) *Military wall* is demarcated in Brown with emphasis in Red;
 - h) Regions are delimited by a polygon of the color assigned to that region and with a double-color prism (color assigned to the region + white) and name;
 - i) Sectors are identified by the acronym S+n^o;
 - j) Main cities of the sectors are identified with a blue prism;
- 10) All this information can be found in the legend dedicated to the semiology of the map, which is located at the bottom of the map;
- 11) Additional information contained in the reports is placed in a section called *Most Attacked Location*;

- 12) Once the construction of the Map is completed, two files are issued:
- a) 1 (one) PNG:
 - i. In the PNG version, is added one extra element, designated as *Highlight of the Week*. A small map showing the location with the most attacks or with pertinent information;
 1. This Map is outlined by a blue line;
 2. The same delimitation is placed around the sector in the map legend;
 - ii. PNG file is added to the Excel sheet, and immediately afterwards a Printing Area is created with the following name: Week X: From dd-mm-yyyy to dd-mm-yyyy, in PDF format;
 - b) 1 (one) PDF;
 - i. Standalone Map;
 - ii. Name: Western Sahara War Map Week X: dd-mm-yyyy to dd-mm-yyyy;
- 13) The Standalone Map, the statistical information and the PDFs of the official *War Communiqués*, are then uploaded onto the Site;
- a) Similar to *Official News* and *Documents*, it is necessary to fill in a form with the following categories:
 - i. Title:
 1. *War Communiqués* in the original language;
 2. Map- Western Sahara War Map Week X: dd-mm-yyyy to dd-mm-yyyy;
 3. Excel- War Report Week X: dd-mm-yyyy to dd-mm-yyyy;
 - ii. PDF;
 1. The upload is done separately, that is, each PDF is individually inserted into the platform, following the subsequent logic:
 - a) *War Communiqués* (one by one);
 - b) Map;
 - c) Excel;
 - iii. Link to the official *War Communiqué*;
 1. *War Communiqué* only;
 - iv. Original date of the official *War Communiqué*;
 1. *War Communiqué* only;
 2. Map and Excel - Date of the upload;
 - v. Issuer:
 1. SPS- *War Communiqué*;
 2. CEAUP- Maps and Excel;
 - vi. Language of Emission:
 1. *War Communiqué* - Spanish;
 2. Maps and Excel- English;
 - vii. Country of Emission:
 1. *War Communiqué* – Western Sahara;
 2. Maps and Excel- Portugal;
 - viii. Typology:
 1. *Documents- Official War Communiqués*;
 2. *War Data/Maps- PDF Maps*;
 3. *War Data/Military Data- Excel PDF*;
 - ix. *Key words/Tags*;
 - x. The cartographic data created in *QGIS*, in a second phase, are imported into the *ArcGIS*, so it can be displayed in an interactive format, on the *Home Page* of the Site.

This team is also responsible for, the statistical treatment of the metadata generated by the News Team. The main intention is to understand which are the main broadcasting languages, the format and in which country they were broadcast. In this way, it is possible to understand the real scale of the information about the conflict.

The data will be processed in the following form:

- 1) It will be used the News Team division:
 1. *Official Documents*:
 - a) Will be treated under the umbrella of *Political Data* in the *War Data Menu*;
 - b) Statistical Treatment:
 - i. Counting: presented in a Table Format;
 - ii. Percentage: presented in a Circular Graph Format;
 2. *Articles*:
 - a) Will be treated under the umbrella of *Media Data* in the *War Data Menu*;
 - b) Statistical Treatment:
 - i. It will be divided into:
 1. *News Typology*;
 - a) Counting: presented in a Table Format;
 - b) Percentage: presented in a Circular Graph Format;
 2. *Country of Emission*;
 - a) Counting: presented in a Table Format;
 - b) Visualization: presented in a World Map Format with blue circles representing the totality in each country;
 3. *Language of Publish*;
 - a) Counting: presented in a Table Format;
 - b) Percentage: presented in a Circular Graph Format;

In the last counting performed, the following data were obtained:

1. There was a total of 102 news collected;
2. 8 languages were counted;
3. Spanish was the most common language of publish with 29 record news, follow by English with 28 recorded news, and French, with 25 recorded news;
4. The most found support was Digital with 114 news items;
5. Europe was the region with the most published news, with 73, followed by Morocco with 13, and Africa with 12;
6. The country with the most news recorded was Spain with 22, followed by Morocco with 13, France with 11 and Germany with 10. In comparison, Western Sahara only issued 7 news;
7. 77% of all Official Documentation were issued by SADR, with a total of 68 documents issued, follow by Europe, with 10%, 9 documents issued, and Africa with 8%, 7 documents issued. In comparison, Morocco only issued 1 official document;

8. A new count will be done in the following months, proceeding the publications of this report.

c) Twitter Team

Due to the specificity of the *Social Media Team*, the elements that make up the team, first collect the data using a *Social Network Analysis Software*, in this case, the *NodeXL* program, in order to collect the desired information on *Twitter*.

This social network was chosen, solely and exclusively, because it allows access to an *API Key*, for researchers and research centers. The *API Key* together with *NodeXL*, allows the collection of a set of data, based on the following **keywords**:

WesternSahara; SaharaOccidental; POLISARIO;

The collected data are transferred to an Excel sheet, and then run in the *R Program*, a statistical program, which reads the metadata and transforms them into statistical files. These are the ones that are published on the website and, like the previous teams, it is necessary to fill out a form with the following categories:

1. Title in English;
 - a) Twitter Analysis Week X: dd-mm-yyyy to dd-mm-yyyy;
2. PDF;
 - b) Date of the last day of data collection;
3. Issuer:
 - c) CEAUP
4. Language of Emission:
 - d) English
5. Country of Emission:
 - e) Portugal
6. *Key words/Tags*;

4.2. Composition

As already discussed in point 3.a) *Conceptualization of the Idea*, the team was designed to contain several fields of intervention and research, which, until funding was obtained, would be working on a voluntary basis. Something that became clear throughout the development of the project was that it would be essential to integrate more elements within the team, as the workload demanded.

In order to make the project as advantageous as possible, that is, increase its visibility and reach, without ever compromising the quality of work and academic quality, it was presented to a Master's Degree class, in Political Science, and a Bachelor's Degree class, in History, in its first semester of activity, and to an International Master's Degree class in African Studies, in its second semester of activity.

The intention was the integration of students, who were willing to work on an active research project. On the other hand, students were offered:

- A) Access to a group of experienced researchers, through their integration in the work teams, in a non-fixed way and chosen by the students;
- B) The possibility of understanding the functioning of a research project in History and Social Sciences;
- C) Availability and access to work methodologies in History, Geography and Statistics Applied to Social Sciences;
- D) Processing of statistical data;
- E) Initial and continuing training throughout the course;
- F) Access to the most varied programs in use by the team;
- G) Possibility of integration in the team after the end of the semester.

The aim was to demonstrate to students the various problems and phases that a research project has. As well as providing them with means and methodologies for solving problems, understanding the information production chain, the chain of transformation of loose data into understandable data, the chain of transmission of data to the Public.

Consequently, several approaches and presentations were made, over a period of several weeks, in class's, in which the theme of this discipline and the theme of project work were interconnected. The first presentation consisted only of the presentation of the project and was made by a member of the team and the Project Manager. The second presentation already had the presence of the Team Leaders, and it was a longer presentation, as the composition and tasks of the teams were discussed.

This approach has always been without any compromise on either side. Enabling, in a simple and fast way, the presentation of the project and the assimilation of the students, who, after a period of reflection, showed interest in integrating the project.

As the project was well received by the students, they began to integrate it into the teams they wanted. Starting training, within a period not exceeding two weeks after joining the team, and in a timeframe agreed with their Team Leader. The time spent with the students' training was not counted, and this quantification was irrelevant, since it was intended that the students interact with the various elements of the teams, in order to raise doubts, not only about the theme of the work, but also methodological. The most important thing was the quality of the learning.

News Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Largest Team • At least 5 elements • Team Leader + at least 4 elements
Statistics Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composed of 3-4 elements • Team Leader + 2-3 elements
Twitter Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smaller Team • One Element • Team Leader

Table 1- Team's Composition's

4.3. Results

Below you can see a list of data published by the 3 (three) work teams:

News Team	Statistics and Maps Team	Twitter Team	Total of Publications
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles: 1569 Morocco's : 30 SARD: 325 UN: 34 Europe: 48 Africa: 41 America: 4 Asia: 3 Oceania: 1 Total: 2055 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maps: 33 War Communiqués Analysis: 49 Analysis of Political Documents: 2 Analysis of Published Articles: 6 Total: 90 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis: 38 Total: 38 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total: 2183

Table 2-- Publications per Team

Total de Publicações no site WSWA (%)

Graphic 1- Total of Publications in the WSWA Site (%)

A total of 2183 publications were made, and the vast majority of publications were published on the website by the News Team, about 94% of the total, even when considering the *War Communiqués*.

5. Difficulties

Matrix 1-Main Difficulties

6. Project Objectives

Figure 11- Project Objectives

7. Evaluation

In this point, the metrics used to evaluate the performance of the project in the first 12 (twelve) months of activity will be outlined and discussed. These metrics are presented in the table below:

Project Evaluation Metrics Meanings

Total Clicks-Total of Clicks means the total number of actions, one click, that the website received after its presentation in search engines in the last 12 months

Total of Prints - Total of Prints means the number of times the site appeared as a result of a search in search engines in the last 12 months

Main link text - Main link text is understood to be the set of words or phrases, used in the last 12 months, which, when written in search engines, led to the appearance of the site in the results

Click-to-Print Ratio - Click-to-Print Ratio is the percentage of times a Print led to a Click, in the last 12 months

Average Search Engine Position - Average Search Engine Position means the average position in the last 12 months in which the Site appeared on the results page after a search on search engines

Main Country of Search for the Website - Main Country of search for the Website, the country that had the most clicks, in the click/impression ratio, in the last 12 months

Country that generated the most Prints- the Country that generated the most Prints is understood to be the country in which, in a search in search engines, the site appeared as one of the possible results, in the last 12 months

Main linking site - it is understood as Main linking site, the site that has no relationship with the project, but that in the last 12 months, had a link that directs directly to the Project Site

Main Device Used - Main Device Used means the device most used by users who have visited the site in the last 12 months

Date with the most clicks - the date with the most clicks is the date on which the ratio of impressions/clicks generated the most clicks on the site in the last 12 months

Date with the most Prints - It is understood as the Date with the most Prints, as the date on which the project website appeared more times as one of the results of a search in search engines, in the last 12 months

Total External Links - it is understood as Total External Links, the existence of links to the project site on other sites, in the last 12 months

Most visited page - The most visited page is understood to be the page on the website that had the most clicks in the last 12 months

Table 3- Project Evaluation Metrics Meanings

The mentioned ratios are important because, they allow us to perceive the real interaction between the act of research and the click to enter the site. The average calculations of these ratios made it possible to understand whether the communication strategy is working or not. It will also be important, to determine in which regions of the globe the site appears the most as a result of a search, and in which country that search results in a click. Another important factor is, in what position the site appears in a search engine's results listing.

Another important piece of information is knowing which dates are most viewed and which dates the site appeared more often in a search engine search. This information allows us to know which were the acts or news that most impacted the search for information about *Western Sahara*.

Therefore, these were the results in the first twelve months of the project's existence:

Project Evaluation Metrics Results

Total Clicks- 195 clicks in the last 12 months

Total Prints obtained- 16,700 impressions in the last 12 months

Main linking text- Western Sahara War Archives, was the linking text that generated the most impressions in the last 12 months

Click-to-Impression Ratio (CTR)- 1.2% of clicks per impression in the last 12 months

Average position in search engines- 30th Average Search Engine Page Results Option in the last 12 months

Main Country Search for the Site- Spain, with 35 clicks on 1762 impressions in the last 12 months

Country that generated the Most Prints- United States of America, with 2274 impressions in the last 12 months

Main linking site- Porunsaharalibre.org, with 5948 impressions in the last 12 months

Main device used- Computer, with 97 clicks out of 9979 impressions in the last 12 months

Date with the Most Clicks- 26/06/2021

Date with Most Prints- 16/06/2021

Total External Links- 5999 in the last 12 months

Most visited page- Home page, with 28 clicks in the last 12 months

Table 4- Project Evaluation Metrics Results

Figure 12- Total clicks compared to Total traffic in the last 12 months

A total of 195 clicks and a total of 16,700 Prints were obtained, with a *CTR* of 1.2% and an average position of 30 search results. In terms of analysis, a good average *CTR* is around 1.91% overall and 5.46% for academic searches aided by *Google Ads*. Therefore, the site is 0.7% below the average *CTR* and 3.55% of academic searches helped by *Google Ads*.

As there is no specific metric of direct comparison, we accept the differences as natural results of both the theme specificity (*War*), the location (*Western Sahara*) and the fact that we do not use the *Google Ads* engine. Therefore, we can consider this a good result, with room for growth. And this is indicated when we consider the average position in search engines, 30, and the total number of impressions.

Figure 13- Average CTR compared to Average Position

PROJECT MONITORING REPORT: WESTERN SAHARA WAR ARCHIVES – A MONITORING DATABASE FOR THE II WAR IN WESTERN SAHARA

CONSULTAS	PÁGINAS	PAÍSES	DISPOSITIVOS	ASPETO DA PESQUISA	DATAS			
					Cliques	Impressões	CTR	Posição
Data								
26/06/2021					4	211	1.9%	34.9
05/11/2021					4	88	4.5%	25.2
05/06/2021					4	84	4.8%	26.1
21/06/2021					3	210	1.4%	31.6
27/06/2021					3	169	1.8%	34.3
10/06/2021					3	166	1.8%	29.9
24/06/2021					3	161	1.9%	25.7
07/06/2021					3	144	2.1%	25.5
06/06/2021					3	107	2.8%	25.2
14/07/2021					3	79	3.8%	24.1

Figure 14- Date with the most clicks

The date with the most clicks was 26/06/2021 with 4 clicks out of 211 impressions, with a CTR of 1.9% and an average position of 34.9. We note that on June 23, the *High Commissioner for Human Rights* reiterated the need to reactivate a program of visits to the occupied territories, which had been suspended since 2015, due to the intentional obstruction of Morocco. This may have been the reason for the increase in searches.

However, the date with the most prints was 16/06/2021, with 2 clicks out of 254 Prints, with a CTR of 0.8% and an average position of 30.

CONSULTAS	PÁGINAS	PAÍSES	DISPOSITIVOS	ASPETO DA PESQUISA	DATAS			
					Cliques	Impressões	CTR	Posição
Data								
16/06/2021					2	254	0.8%	30
15/06/2021					0	237	0%	30.3
25/06/2021					2	214	0.9%	36.3
26/06/2021					4	211	1.9%	34.9
21/06/2021					3	210	1.4%	31.6
14/06/2021					2	210	1%	30.8
17/06/2021					1	210	0.5%	28.2
11/06/2021					2	201	1%	31.5
28/06/2021					1	194	0.5%	31.9
13/06/2021					1	187	0.5%	28.1

Figure 15- Date with the most Prints

Finally, about 5999 external links were counted, that is, there are this total number of links on sites outside the project, which lead directly to the project site. This list is headed by *Porunsaharalibre.org*, with 5948 links. In second place is the *African.eu* website (the CEAUP website), with 23 links. The third place is occupied by *nodexlgraphygallery.org*, the website of the program used by the *Twitter Team*, with 7 links. Followed by a series of websites and blogs connected with *Diaspora* or associations in support of the Saharawi cause. Finally, we emphasize that the compilation of the words *Western Sahara War Archives* was the text, or variations of it, most used to search for the Site. The other options being: *war data*; *frente polsario briefing on the situation in guergarat*; *رشيف الغربية الصحراء في الحرب* (which means *www.westernsahara-wa.com* in Arabic); *el archivo de guerra del sáhara occidental* (Western Sahara war archive in Spanish); *westsahara kriegsarchiv* (Western Sahara war archive in German); *13 november 2020*.

CONSULTAS	PÁGINAS	PAÍSES	DISPOSITIVOS	ASPETO DA PESQUISA	DATAS		
Páginas principais				↓ Cliques	Impressões	CTR	Posição
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/				28	472	5.9%	13.9
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Le-CCG-reconnait-la-marocanité-du-Sahara.pdf				4	133	3%	20.4
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Error-de-cálculo-y-huida-hacia-delante_-_Marruecos-está-teniendo-un-berrinche-diplomático_.pdf				4	95	4.2%	16.5
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Western-Sahara-War-Map-Week-33_-_21-06-2021-27-06-2021.pdf				4	32	12.5%	26.5
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/le-journal-espagnol-la-raison-lalgerie-a-finance-brahim-ghali-et-arme-le-polsario/				3	74	4.1%	8.1
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/le-maroc-ouvre-une-double-crise-diplomatique-avec-lallemagne-et-lespagne/				3	64	4.7%	49.2
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Polisario_Sid-Ahmed-Batal-assassine-par-des-fideles-du-general-Said-Chengriha.pdf				3	36	8.3%	15.5
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/war-data/				3	31	9.7%	9.3
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/AMPLIACIÓN_-_Un-ataque-marroquí-con-proyectiles-alcanza-una-zona-civil-fronteriza-que-da-acceso-a-los-campamentos-de-refugiados-saharauis_.pdf				2	301	0.7%	9.8
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Sahara-Marocain_-_La-République-du-Salvador-décide-douvrir-un-Consulat-Général-à-Leáyoune_-_Le7tv.ma_.pdf				2	275	0.7%	7.2

Figure 18- Page with the most clicks

CONSULTAS	PÁGINAS	PAÍSES	DISPOSITIVOS	ASPETO DA PESQUISA	DATAS		
Dispositivo				↓ Cliques	Impressões	CTR	Posição
Computador				97	9 979	1%	36.9
Telemóvel				94	6 566	1.4%	20
Tablet				4	184	2.2%	16.7

Figure 20 – Most used devices

Páginas de ligação principais	
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/	5 997
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/frente-polisario-briefing-on-the-situation-in-guergarat/	1
https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/war-data/	1

Figure 19- Top linking pages, last 12 months

Total de links externos

5 999

Figure 22- Total external links counted for in the last 12 months

Principais sites de ligação	
porunsaharalibre.org	5 948
africanos.eu	23
nodexlgraphygallery.org	7
ecsaharai.com	4
noteolvidesdelsaharaoccidental.org	3

Figure 21- Top linking sites in the last 12 months

Principal texto de ligação ⓘ

↑ Classificação	Texto do link
1	western sahara war archive
2	(vazio)
3	https www westernsahara wa com
4	westernsahara wa com
5	http www westernsahara wa com
6	war data
7	2 westernsahara wa com
8	1 westernsahara wa com
9	3 westernsahara wa com
10	the western sahara war archive
11	frente polissario briefing on the situation in guergarat
12	home westernsahara wa
13	أرشيف الحرب في الصحراء الغربية https www westernsahara wa com
14	westsahara kriegsarchiv
15	navigate to website westernsahara wa com
16	el archivo de guerra del sahara occidental
17	13 november 2020

Figure 23- Top link text, last 12 months

8. Future Actions

Looking at the main problems encountered, the proposed objectives, the evaluation metrics and their results, we can conclude that the project, in the first 12 (twelve) months of life, is performing in line with expectations, having plenty of room to grow.

Therefore, we dedicate this point to outlining some guidelines for actions for the next 12 (twelve) months:

1. Investing in the short-term expansion of the *News Team* within a period, never exceeding, 3 months;
2. Consider a greater integration of students into the project;
3. Publish the Glossary of Names and Meanings, in the short-medium term, between 3-6 months;
4. Publish a more in-depth statistical analysis report on data related to the War, in the short-medium term, between 3-6 months;
5. Develop a Communicative Strategy, in order to transform more Impressions into Clicks, increasing the *CTR*, in the short-medium term, between 3-6 months;
6. In the long term, in a period between 6-12 months, establish more partnerships with other institutions in order to increase the visibility of the Site;
7. In the short-medium term, within a period not exceeding 6 months, try to hold an academic conference to present the results of the site;
8. Incorporate an element capable of analyzing news, in order to detect Fake News;
9. Perform a meta-analysis within Twitter, in order to understand the interaction between the CEAUP team posts, repost and likes;
10. Perform a new analysis within 12 months;

Conclusion

When the war in *Western Sahara* reignited, the *CEAUP*, a study center based in the *FLUP*, focused on African affairs, aware of the political situation surrounding *Western Sahara*, raised a set of questions regarding the treatment that war information could come to have.

The project developed was an information aggregator site, called *Western Sahara War Archives*, with the following link: <https://www.westernsahara-wa.com/>. The intention was to collect reliable information from known sources such as *Lusa*, *Der Spiegel*, *Washington Post*, *UN*, *AU*, *NATO*, and cross this information with statistical data produced by the team, based on official reports and documents, in order to understand how the subject of the War was not only being communicated, but also in what way, to whom, in what languages, with what sources, ...

Throughout this report, the procedures used by the three work teams were presented, as well as the ways of evaluating the project, the performance metrics and the values that were obtained during its first year of activity.

Therefore, for the period under analysis, a total of 2055 news items were analyzed, 90 statistical analysis documents and 38 analysis documents from the social media *Twitter*, in a total of 2183 publications.

Regarding the traffic obtained by the site, there were a total of 195 clicks and a total of 16,700 prints, with a *CTR* of 1.2% and an average position of 30 search results. The country of origin with the most clicks is Spain, with 35 clicks out of 1762 prints, with a *CTR* of 2% and an average position of 16. While the *United States of America* was the country where the most prints were generated, 2274, 11 clicks, a *CTR* of 0.5% and an average position of 39.5. The most visited page was the *Home Page* with 28 clicks, 472 prints, a *CTR* of 5.9% and an average position of 13.9. The most used device to visit was the *Personal Computer*, with 97 clicks, 9979 prints, 1% *CTR* and an average position of 36.9. About 5999 external links to the site were counted.

Taking into account all the problems encountered during the project, their specificity, the project fulfilled its primary and secondary objectives. Starting its second year of activity with very encouraging and positive results. As there is no benchmark for a comparative assessment of the site's performance, due to its specificity, this report will serve as a future benchmark for projects of similar scope. It will serve as an element of performance evaluation, through a direct comparison between the results obtained in this second evaluation with the results described in this report.